

REALIZATION OF LINGUISTIC AND CULTURAL UNITS**Turaboyeva Sitora Zokirovna**

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Annotation: This article divides linguistic and cultural units into certain groups, each of which is illustrated with examples. Adequate and equivalent concepts of each lexeme and differences and similarities between them are analyzed separately.

Key words: Linguistic, Equivalent, lexeme, adequate, lexical-semantic.

Linguistic units can be divided into two large groups. In this case, we can include in the first classification units related to culture and existing in real life in the form of objects, events, actions and verbalized materiality. Examples of Uzbek linguistic and cultural units are doppi, chapon, tandir, mahalla, elder, mahsi-kalish, somsa, sumalak, sovchilik, and speed-dating, thanksgiving day, boxing day, chicken tikka masala, etc. Units of this type are also characterized by the fact that they can be exactly adequate or partially equivalent to each other. In some cases, units that are considered adequate are not considered adequate according to all aspects of semantic meaning. We can compare this with the example of the process term verbalized in the form of the wedding lexeme, which has a great place in Uzbek culture, and its English translation, wedding.

In the Uzbek language, the linguo-cultural unit of the wedding is equivalent to the lexeme wedding in English. This unit is explained in the "Annotated Dictionary of the Uzbek Language" as follows:

1. The general name of folk ceremonies that are held with feasts and spectacles with marriage, marriage, circumcision and other relationships;
2. In accordance with the agreement between the suitors, a set of money, sarpo, material and the like given by the groom to the girl;
3. In connection with the sending of these things, a ceremony will be held in the groom's house and the bride's house;

4. Celebrations dedicated to an event with feasts and entertainment."

In English, the equivalent of wedding is —"Longman English dictionary" —...1. A ceremony in which two people get married;

1a. referring to a wedding: wedding present/ring/sake/reception;

2. BrE a wedding anniversary.

In each of the above interpretations of the wedding lexeme, it is understood that it is a ceremony related to reciprocity, that is, marriage. It is observed that the process related to the wedding is in the form of a feast in both cultures. However, in the explanatory dictionary of the Uzbek language, the existence of such components as circumcision is not reflected in the semantic field of wedding, which is taken as adequate for the lexeme of wedding. Also, the second explanation given to the equivalent unit of wedding (a set of money, sarpo, material, etc. given by the groom to the girl in accordance with the agreement between the grooms) is not found in the explanation of the lexeme wedding in English. In Uzbek culture, when the day of the wedding ceremony is set, the groom's family sends a gift to the bride's house a day or two before the wedding day to celebrate the wedding. The composition of the gift consists of money, sarpo and food products.

In connection with the arrival of a wedding (gift) to the bride's house, her dowry is sent to the groom. A dowry is a gift given to a girl by her parents and relatives, and it usually consists of items. Based on the above examples, it can be said that the absence of the combination of money, sarpo, material, etc. given by the groom to the girl in accordance with the agreement between the bridegroom and the wedding lexeme in Uzbek is explained by the lack of such a situation in the structure of the culture. For this reason, when a semantic meaning considered adequate or equivalent in a certain sense is taken in a second or other context in linguistic and cultural units, mutual differences are observed according to the nature of functionality.

As an example, there are cases where the linguistic and cultural unit wedding is used in a figurative or metaphorical sense when it occurs in the

discourse. In this case, this unit is used in the sense of joy, victory, good day, and the figurative meaning is understood only when it is taken into general analysis within the context.

Equivalent linguocultural units not only record intercultural compatibility, but also reveal their distinguishing features. In the comparison of languages, lexical units that are similar in form, but whose content components are not similar to each other, are congruent phenomena; Although not similar in form, lexical units whose content components are consistent with each other create the phenomenon of equivalence. The phenomenon of equivalence describes the relationship of two corresponding units, but these units do not form all connections. Each thing in the universe characterizes its own sign, and this thing is not uniformly perceived by representatives of one or another culture. For this reason, representatives of different nationalities can trace different "traces" behind the same concept.

An equivalent unit is a national-cultural word or phrase that does not exist in the structural components of the corresponding equivalent in the language under comparison, and it is a lexical unit that does not form exactly with the same national-cultural component.

In English, the lack of a combination of money, sarpo, material, etc. given by the groom to the girl in accordance with the agreement between the bridegroom and the equivalent of the wedding in Uzbek is explained by the absence of such a situation in English culture. Functionality is also observed in linguistic and cultural units. In this case, the resulting unit can be used in one or more meanings that are not related to culture, while reflecting traits related to a particular culture. The description of the wedding lexeme given in the explanatory dictionary of the Uzbek language also proves our opinion. But there are no cases where the lexeme wedding in English is used in the semantic sense given above.

1. Satisfy the need for food and drink, eat, drink, eat and drink. A bird that does not eat enough cannot be satisfied with a lick.(Proverb)

2. Satisfy yourself with water and food. (about land and plants) The cotton is saturated with water. The hand is not satisfied until the earth is satisfied. (proverb)
3. Literally. Enjoy and enjoy. I fell asleep. I can't get enough of Diidorin.
4. Literally. Tired of enduring and enduring. To be a bully. Act wisely and honestly, we are fed up now. A. Qadiri.

"The days gone by"

On the basis of the analyzed examples, it can be concluded that the linguistic and cultural units present in each language cannot be separated from the linguistic characteristics of the language in question. Along with the recognition of language as a cultural phenomenon, special units that reflect the cultural values of the nation and "emboss" the national character are grouped separately in its system. Such units mean ethnic, socio-cultural views, national traditions, customs, manners, communication standards, etc. specific to a particular nation. Language units that include such extralinguistic information are called national-cultural units. V. V. Vorobev proposed to express such units with the term *lingvokulturema*. In his opinion, this term covers not only the linguistic meaning of the language unit, but also the cultural segment.

As a separate group of linguistic and cultural units, the units that are often based on reality or have a material basis and can be felt through our sense organs are considered to have a number of lexical-semantic classifications. *Lacuna* and *realia* stand out among them.